

The cold benzene extract of the powdered heartwood of *Atalantia monophylla* on column chromatography over silica gel afforded an acid fraction (5%). The glc analysis of its methyl ester showed three major peaks corresponding to palmitic, stearic and arachidic methyl esters in the ratio 8 : 4 : 1, as well as minute quantities of C₁₉ acids. The mass spectra of the acid mixture showed three M⁺ peaks at m/e 256 (palmitic), 284 (stearic) and 312 (arachidic) and fragmentation peaks at regular interval of 14 mass units.

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Constituents of *Eupatorium riparium* Regel

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IN course of our studies on the chemical constituents of some Indian medicinal plants we investigated on the whole plant of *E. riparium* which has led to the isolation of taraxasteryl palmitate (I), taraxasteryl acetate (II), *epi*-friedelinol (III) and stigmasterol. Earlier work on the plant *E. riparium* Regel, however, resulted in the isolation of taraxasteryl palmitate, taraxasterol and stigmasterol¹ and chromones^{2,3}. This is thus the first report of the isolation of taraxasteryl acetate (II) and *epi*-friedelinol (III) from *E. riparium*.

Air-dried milled whole plant of *E. riparium* (3 kg) collected from the sub-Himalayan range in the month of April, 1976 was percolated with light petrol at room temperature for 10 days. The marc was again extracted exhaustively with chloroform at room temperature by percolation. Both extracts were concentrated separately by distilling off the solvent.

Taraxasteryl palmitate (I), *epi*-friedelinol (III) and stigmasterol were isolated from the petrol

extract. Taraxasteryl palmitate¹(I), C₄₆H₈₀O₂ (M⁺ 664.6171), m.p. 95°, [α]_D +70° (CHCl₃, c 0.17) was isolated as colourless needles (3 g, 0.1%) (petrol-acetone) from the petrol eluates during the chromatographic separation of the petrol extract over silica gel. It showed positive TNM colouration and exhibited ir (KBr) bands at 1722 (C=O), 1630 (C=C) and 860 cm⁻¹ (C=CH₂); ¹H nmr signals (CDCl₃) at δ 4.60 (2H, m, C=CH₂), 4.45 (1H, m, >CH-O-CO-), 2.26 (2H, t, J=6Hz, -CH₂COO-) and ¹³C nmr signals (CDCl₃) at δ 173.4 (CO), 154.3 (C-20), 107.1 (C-30), 80.5 (C-3), 55.4 (C-5), 50.3 (C-9), 48.6 (C-18), 42.0 (C-14), 40.9 (C-8), 39.2 (C-22 or C-16), 39.1 (C-16 or C-22), 38.8 (C-13), 38.4 (C-19 and C-1), 37.7 (C-4), 37.0 (C-10), 34.7 (C-2'), 34.4 (C-17), 33.9 (C-7), 31.9 (C-14'), 29.6 (C-4' to C-13'), 27.9 (C-23), 26.6 (C-15), 26.1 (C-28), 25.6 (C-12 and C-21), 25.1 (C-3'), 23.7 (C-2), 22.6 (C-15'), 21.4 (C-11), 19.4 (C-29), 18.1 (C-6 and C-16'), 16.5 (C-24), 16.2 (C-26), 15.9 (C-25) and 14.7 (C-27).

I on saponification with 5% KOH afforded taraxasterol (IV), C₃₀H₅₀O (M⁺ 426), m.p. 218°, [α]_D +55° (CHCl₃, c 0.17). It gave Lieberman Burchard colouration reaction for triterpenes and showed ν_{\max} (KBr) at 3400 (OH), 1633, 870 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr signals (CDCl₃) at δ 4.62 (2H, d, J=2.2 Hz, C=CH₂), 3.22 (1H, m, CHOH), 1.05, 1.01, 0.97, 0.94, 0.93, 0.85 and 0.76 (21H, seven singlets, methyl protons) and ¹³C nmr signals (CDCl₃) at δ 154.4 (C-20), 107.0 (C-30), 78.9 (C-3), 55.3 (C-5), 50.4 (C-9), 48.5 (C-18), 41.9 (C-14), 40.8 (C-8), 39.2 (C-22 or C-16), 39.1 (C-16 or C-22), 38.7 (C-1 and C-13), 38.2 (C-19), 37.0 (C-10), 34.4 (C-17), 34.0 (C-7), 27.9 (C-23), 27.3 (C-2), 26.6 (C-15), 26.1 (C-28), 25.5 (C-12 or C-21), 25.4 (C-21 or C-12), 21.3 (C-11), 19.3 (C-29), 18.2 (C-6), 16.1 (C-26), 15.8 (C-25), 15.2 (C-24) and 14.6 (C-27). IV was identical with an authentic sample of taraxasterol (m. m. p., ir and co-tlc).

IV on acetylation formed taraxasteryl acetate (II), C₃₂H₅₂O₂ (M⁺ 468), m.p. 243°, [α]_D +99° (CHCl₃, c 0.16) which exhibited ν_{\max} (KBr) at 1732, 1245 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr signals (CDCl₃) at δ 4.61 (2H, d, J=2.2 Hz, C=CH₂), 4.46 (1H, m, CHOAc), 1.07, 1.02, 0.98, 0.93, 0.88, 0.85 and 0.85 (21H, seven singlets, methyl protons) and ¹³C nmr chemical shifts (CDCl₃) at δ 170.8 (C=O), 154.4 (C-20), 107.0 (C-30), 80.8 (C-3), 55.4 (C-5), 50.3 (C-9), 48.6 (C-18), 41.9 (C-14), 40.8 (C-8), 39.3 (C-22 or C-16), 39.1 (C-16 or C-22), 38.8 (C-13), 38.4 (C-1), 38.3 (C-19), 37.7 (C-4), 37.0 (C-10), 34.4 (C-17), 33.9 (C-7), 27.8 (C-23), 26.6 (C-15), 26.1 (C-28), 25.5 (C-12 or C-21), 25.4 (C-21 or C-12), 23.6 (C-2), 21.4 (C-11), 21.1 (COCH₃), 19.4 (C-29), 18.1 (C-6), 16.4 (C-24), 16.2 (C-26), 15.8 (C-25) and 14.6 (C-27). The above data and high resolution mass spectrum of I were in conformity with its assigned structure. The assignment of the various chemical shifts of I, II and IV were made by comparison with the resonances for

germanicol acetate⁴ and lupeol⁵ and following the chemical shift theory.

The benzene eluted fractions of the same chromatogram afforded *epi*-friedelinol^{6,7} (III), C₃₀H₅₂O (M⁺ 428), m. p. 268°, [α]_D +19.3° (CHCl₃, c 0.103) as crystalline compound (0.15 g, 0.005%). It showed positive LB colouration reaction for triterpenes and exhibited ν_{\max} (KBr) at 3500 (OH), 2930, 1378 and 1352 cm⁻¹ (*gem*-dimethyl). On acetylation it gave *epi*-friedelinyl acetate (V), C₃₂H₅₄O₂ (M⁺ 470), m. p. 285°, [α]_D +33° (CHCl₃, c 0.17). V exhibited ν_{\max} at 1732, 1245 and 978 cm⁻¹ and ¹³C nmr signals⁸ (CDCl₃) at δ 170.7 (C=O), 74.5 (C-3), 60.9 (C-10), 53.1 (C-8), 48.0 (C-4), 42.8 (C-18), 41.6 (C-6), 39.6 (C-14 or C-13), 39.2 (C-22), 38.3 (C-13 or C-14), 37.8 (C-5), 37.0 (C-9), 36.0 (C-16), 35.5 (C-19), 35.3 (C-11), 34.9 (C-29), 32.8 (C-21), 32.3 (C-15 or C-12), 32.1 (C-2), 32.0 (C-28), 31.7 (C-30), 30.5 (C-12 or C-15), 29.9 (C-17), 28.1 (C-20), 21.2 (CH₃CO), 20.0 (C-27), 18.5 (C-26), 18.1 (C-25), 17.6 (C-7), 16.3 (C-1), 15.7 (C-24) and 11.2 (C-23). All these data established IV as *epi*-friedelinol which was further confirmed by its direct comparison (superimposable ir, m. m. p. and co-tlc) with an authentic sample.

The chloroform eluted fractions of the main chromatogram afforded a sterol crystallizing from chloroform-acetone as colourless needles, m.p. 155°. It was found identical with stigmasterol by direct comparison with an authentic sample (m.m.p., ir and co-tlc).

The chloroform extract of *E. riparium* on chromatographic resolution over silica gel afforded a triterpene from the benzene eluted fractions crystallizing from chloroform-acetone as needles, m. p. 238-40°. This was identical with taraxasteryl acetate (II) in all respects. Besides taraxasteryl acetate, the same chromatogram afforded taraxasteryl palmitate (I), *epi*-friedelinol (III) and stigmasterol from the petrol, benzene and chloroform eluates, respectively.

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Determination of *N-m-Tolyl-p-Methoxy benzo-hydroxamic Acid* and *N-m-Tolyl-p-Chloro-benzo hydroxamic Acid* in Acetone†

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VARIOUS arylhydroxamic acids have been used for solvent extraction and spectrophotometric determination¹⁻⁶ of Nb(V), Ta(V), Ti(IV), Mo(VI), W(VI) etc. *N-m-Tolyl-p-methoxy benzo*hydroxamic acid (TMBHA) and *N-m-tolyl-p-chlorobenzo*hydroxamic acid (TCBHA) have been recently used in our laboratory for solvent extraction and spectrophotometric determination⁷⁻¹⁰ of Nb(V) and Ti(IV). In continuation of our earlier work on estimation of oximes^{11,12}, thiocarbamides¹³ and biuret¹⁴ the present paper deals with quantitative estimation of benzo hydroxamic acids by enthalpic, conductometric and potentiometric titrations. Results obtained by different methods have been compared.

Experimental

Reagents: All chemical were of A. R. grade. Acetone was purified and made anhydrous as usual¹⁵. The titrants, tetra-*n*-butyl ammonium hydroxide (TBuNH₄OH), potassium hydroxide in isopropyl alcohol (Alc. KOH) and potassium tertiary butoxide in tertiary butyl alcohol (*tert* BuOK) were prepared and preserved as reported earlier¹⁵. TMBHA (m. p. 112°, Mol. Wt. 256) and TCBHA (m.p. 138°, Mol. Wt. 261) were prepared by coupling ethereal solution of freshly prepared *N-m-tolyl* hydroxyl amine with corresponding acid chloride at 0°. The products were recrystallised from benzene-petroleum ether (40°-60°).

Instruments and procedures: A direct reading potentiometer was used for potentiometric titrations. Calomel electrode, prepared with Hg/HgCl₂

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